

VIRTUAL PLACEMENT CELL FOR HEI

Varun Shenoy* & Dr. P. S. Aithal**

College of Management and Commerce*, Srinivas University**

City Campus Pandeshwar, Mangalore – 575001

varun_shenoy@rediffmail.com

Abstract

Placement Assistance is one of the most important services that HEI's (Higher Educational Institutions) provide to their students. This assistance however will be active only if there is a constant interaction between the placement cell and students on continuous levels. Between, placement seeking students require 24/7, 365 days counselling guidance on clearing the interview considering today's market scenario and securing the job where manpower-based placement cell at HEI's following college timing may not cater. Therefore to bridge this gap and ensure full time assistance to students and alumni even when they are at home, we envision a concept of Virtual Placement Assistance online imparting every nut and bolt essential for the true blue placement, from basic Group Discussions tips to Aptitude Tests or Pros and Cons of Interviews as well as scheduling interviews both online and offline for the student candidates round the clock.

Keywords : Virtual Placement Cell, Virtual Placement Office, Virtual Placement Assistance, Virtual Placement Support.

I. Introduction

Not all students are intellectually competent in academics and that is why they undertake tutorials and tuitions outside of the college hours. Similarly, not all students are skill-full in clearing campus interviews and are shrewd job hunters at the campus opportunities advanced to them during the academic season. Now, if the academic tuition taking students outside college hours depend on online learning to supplement or aid their studies in college for better academic performance, similarly then weak students with poor employability skills can also depend on 'technology' to strengthen their professional confidence & abilities. A non-location of literature work in this regards and direct interactions with select Job Seeking students helped to determine the research problem. Therefore, we propose a sustainable 'virtual placement assistance cell' like an *online virtual assistant software* for students to understand the methodologies of job hunting and attending interviews at campus for their first entry level jobs.

II. Objectives

The Primary objective of this concept is to assist & satisfy the student population access placement assistance anytime anywhere 24/7, 365 days. The paper also aims to bring in most modern cutting-edge technologies in the area of Graduate Placement Assistance and Administration at Higher Educational Institutions HEI.

III. Research Methodology

Through Brainstorming methodology and rigorous thought process the conceptual idea is propagated. A theoretical and descriptive method of idea generation has been adopted here to explain the concept.

IV. Concept of Virtual Placement Cell

Virtual Placement Cell refers to the process of providing a range of options through the use of various types of technology to job seeking students and graduates in order to connect them with employment related services. It is managed through self-service platforms where placement professors can put data directly into them and skip the process of going through a manual action. Virtual HEI Placement Cell is expected to be practiced due to its cost reduction impact, to gain competitive advantage and to share risks of miscommunication. It is network-based structure initiative built on partnerships and mediated by information technologies to help the HEI acquire, develop, and deploy employment & job related intellectual capital.

Proposed Phases in Virtualization :

(1) Virtualisation of HEI Placement Cell takes place through installation of a 'Chat Bot' through suitable tracking systems using AI, Automation & Robotics Technology to answer and guide job seeking students on College Whatsapp Chat Channels, College Social Media, College Blogs, College Mobile Application, College Website, College SAS post completion of college timings or even during the college time anything and everything on placement campus interview, training and job search related doubts. A 'Chat Bot' is known as an artificial conversational entity (ACE) which is an AI Computer Program that simulates human conversations, texts and provides relevant information and guidance through Natural Language Processing (NLP). In industry, this concept is reminiscent with Robotic Process Automation (RPA). Robotic process automation (RPA) is performing rules-based, highly transactional processes in the HR department that require little or no human judgment. RPA works by having a AI software "bot" take over high-volume, repetitive operational tasks from HR employees, often improving the accuracy and speed of data processing—such as payroll, benefits enrolment, on-boarding and compliance reporting that all require a significant amount of manual, repetitive labour otherwise. It can also navigate ERP Systems and Service Management Software tools using the applicant's user interfaces just like a human operator that too faster!

(2) To have 24/7 access to a cloud-based document library, where job seeking students can download placement notices and job descriptions, including letters and reports that have been drafted specifically for them.

(3) Connect with recruiters HRMS online to use a common platform via cloud or related technologies. This shall help in stakeholder resource integration and sharing of hiring information directly to job seeking students by the recruiters.

Figure 1 : Flow Diagram of Virtual Placement Cell System in HEI's

Thus, Virtual HEI Placement Cell = Application of Robotics/AI + Cloud/ICT + Integration of HRMS that is expected to be compatible across various software platforms for user access and ensured data security with strong encryption and a policy of data protection in place for stakeholder benefit.

Perceived Advantages and Benefits of HEI Placement Cell Virtualization :

- (1) Increased access to the college placement services 24/7, 365 days anytime anywhere leading to student satisfaction.
- (2) 'ChatBots' dependency can bring in student delight as their new e-friend or e-guide for securing placements.
- (3) The concept shall lead to better internal processes leading to a good quality IQAC or NAAC Gradings in HEI Placement Services.
- (4) Better Student Fraud Detection or their intention to deceive.

Forecasted Challenges in HEI Placement Cell Virtualization :

Despite all the benefits, the integration of virtual mobility into HEI placement cell, either as a complete alternative or as a support mechanism, remains challenging. There are several points of interest both at an organisational, pedagogical and technological levels. Conducting virtual placement assistance work requires a mix of technical tools and processes that stimulate emotional connections among students and graduates.

V. Conclusions

We have discussed a workable concept of HEI Placement Cell Virtualization in this paper. A feasibility determination test is hoped through gathering feedback about the new concept

from the appropriate and relevant stakeholders. Writing a proposal to business organizations for implementation of this concept as a commercial service to HEI's is also in contemplation. AI-based applications have strong potential to raise graduate student productivity and help them become new age professionals thus become knowledgeable job seekers that can boost employability. Applications empowered by AI have an ability to analyse, predict, diagnose and become more powerful and capable resources.

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